

INVESTIGATION OF PEEL STRENGTH IN RECYCLABLE SANDWICH PANELS

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1 Introduction

Sandwich construction (strong, stiff facings bonded to a relatively thick, low density core) is common in many structural applications of polymer composites. A wide variety of core materials are used, each having its own advantages and disadvantages. But in the cases of high performance applications, aluminium or Nomex[®] honeycomb is usually specified. Due to the high cost involved in manufacturing of such cores, their applications have been somewhat limited to high end products, such as those in aerospace industries. To address the cost issues and the recent environmental concerns, hollow cores for sandwich panels have been produced from recyclable thermoplastic composites.

The structural integrity, such as the inter-laminar shear and flatwise tensile strengths of these panels, depend on the quality of the bond between facings and the core. As thermoplastic composites are chemically inert, bonding incompatibilities of these composites occur sometimes when they are used together. Traditional bonding methods, such as mechanical fastening and adhesive bonding used in thermoset composites have been extended to bond thermoplastic composites but the efficiency of the bonding system depends on the compatibility of the system with thermoplastics [1]. Moreover, as these processes tend to be difficult and labour intensive, they are not considered as ideal bonding techniques.

An alternative to the above mentioned joining methods is fusion bonding, where the polymer composite is heated at its interface to a viscous state, causing the polymer chains to inter-diffuse physically, maintaining the integrity of the material and reducing the manufacturing time [2]. Induction welding, ultrasonic welding and resistance welding are the three most common fusion bonding techniques for thermoplastics, and ultrasonic

welding is rated as the most efficient process in terms of possible automation.

During ultrasonic bonding, the materials to be bonded are held together under pressure and then subjected to high frequency, vertical vibration. A combination of surface and intermolecular friction generates heat and along with the application of pressure, causes the material to flow. The flowing polymer wets the interface causing diffusion and entanglement of polymer chains across the interface, thereby resulting in a weld [3]. The process is relatively fast and clean due to the absence of chemicals or adhesives involved, and additionally the pre/post curing free and relatively flash free qualities make this an attractive process.

The bond strength of the adherents is measured as the shear strength at the bonded region, which is influenced by many process factors such as weld time, pressure, hold time, frequency and amplitude. Therefore, to obtain consistent welds, it is important to optimise these process variables. However, to study such a complex, multivariable system and its influence on the mechanical properties of the materials individually tends to become tedious, and hence obtaining synergistic effects between the parameters proves to be difficult. Therefore, a full factorial design of experiments (DoE), where these parameters were systematically varied and a statistical analysis based on Taguchi method, was used to understand the interacting effect of these parameters on the shear strength of the bonded joint. The primary objective of this analysis was not to seek a global optimum of the processing conditions, but to determine what parameters were critical to successful bonding.

2 Materials and Manufacturing

2.1 Materials

Radiata Pine wood flour (length/diameter ~ 3) was used as natural fibre reinforcement in as received condition. The fibres were blended with polypropylene (PP) and a copolymer and lubricant (Licocene PP MA 6452 TP). The raw materials were first extruded with the barrel temperature varying from 140-200°C from the feeding to the die end and the torque and screw speed were adjusted until a uniform mix was achieved. The extruded material was air cooled, pelletised and then dried in a dryer for 12 hours. Stitched unidirectional flax fabric obtained from Libeco, Belgium, PP sheets and glass fibre/PP tapes (Plytron™) obtained from local sources were used to manufacture composites for facings.

2.2 Manufacturing of sandwich panels

The compounded material (fibres, talc and polypropylene) was then extruded in a TC35 Cincinnati Milacron extruder through a die of 300mm by 2.5mm rectangular cross-section. The sheets were calendered to obtain thin (0.7mm) continuous rolls of wood-PP composites and then thermoformed into half hexagonal profiles that were cut to required heights and ultrasonically bonded to form hollow cores.

For facings, flax/PP and glass fibre/PP composites with a stacking sequence of [0/90/0] and [0/90/0/90/0], respectively were manufactured using compression moulding. The facings were ultrasonically bonded to the cores to form sandwich panels, Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Ultrasonic bonding of (a) WF/PP core and (b) Plytron face sheets

3 Mechanical testing

Tensile tests to determine the tensile modulus and strength in the longitudinal and transverse directions were carried out according to standard ASTM D638 [4] and those for the Poisson’s ratio, ν_{12} was conducted in accordance with ASTM E132 [5].

Single lap shear test to determine the shear strength of the bond at the nodes and climbing drum peel test to determine the skin-to-core bonding in the sandwich panels were carried out as per standards ASTM D3163 [6] and ASTM D1781 [7], respectively. Four-point bending with two point loads equidistant from the supports was used and the flexural test on flat sandwich panels was carried out as per standard ASTM C 393 [8] and D7250-06 [9]. The results of the mechanical material testing for the WF/PP core are presented in Table.1 and those for the face sheet laminates are listed in Table. 2.

Table.1 Mechanical properties of WF/PP composite

Property		Value
Sheet Density	ρ_s (kg/m ³)	1000
Tensile Strength	σ_1 (MPa)	39.3
	σ_2 (MPa)	26.2
Tensile Modulus	E_1 (GPa)	3.65
	E_2 (GPa)	2.70
Poisson’s Ratio	ν_{12}	0.40

s- sheet; 1- longitudinal; 2- transverse

Table.2 Summary of mechanical properties of flax/PP and Plytron™ laminates

Material Property		Flax/PP	Plytron
Stacking sequence		[0/90/0]	[0/90/0]
Fibre volume fraction		0.35	0.35
Face sheet thickness (mm)		1.95	0.70
Tensile strength	σ_1 (MPa)	90.5	338
	σ_2 (MPa)	45.4	186
Tensile modulus	E_1 (GPa)	4.80	17.5
	E_2 (GPa)	3.78	9.4
Poisson’s ratio, ν_{12}		0.40	0.10

4 Design of Experiment

Ultrasonic welding machine, MP 2022 with a generator (SL20, 20 kHz) was used for ultrasonic bonding. Apart from the fixed frequency, the other parameters, such as weld time, amplitude, distance of the horn from the mating surface and the hold time, could be varied to accommodate different materials. Hence, the bond strength depends on these parameters and to study such a complex, multivariable system and its influence on the mechanical properties of the composites, a full

factorial DoE based on Taguchi method has been considered in this study.

The factors analysed were distance, weld time, amplitude and hold time (Table 2). Distance, D was the distance from the mating surface of the specimens to the horn, measured in percentage thickness of the facing (set to 50% and 75%). Weld time, W was the period the vibration was applied to the specimen (set to 0.6s and 1.0s). Amplitude, A was set to 60 and 90 percent of the maximum amplitude of 22.5µm as determined by the ultrasonic welder’s components.

For each factor, a low and high level was determined, represented numerically by 1 and 2 respectively. To evaluate the effects of these factors, each at two levels, a full factorial DoE with an L₈ orthogonal array was used, Table 3.

Table. 3 L₈ orthogonal arrays

Trial	Levels of Factors			Response y (N)
	D	W	A	
1	1	1	1	333.50
2	1	1	2	383.67
3	1	2	1	442.00
4	1	2	2	524.00
5	2	1	1	281.00
6	2	1	2	314.00
7	2	2	1	396.33
8	2	2	2	475.67

The test specimens for the climbing drum peel test were nominally 76mm wide and 305mm long including 25mm overhang of facing at each end. The test was done by pulling the loading strap at crosshead speed of 25.4 mm/min.

The graphical representation of the Taguchi method of individual factor contribution towards the overall tensile modulus is represented Fig.2. The grand average \bar{y}_{max} of all the trials $y_1 - y_8$ is represented as a horizontal line and then the average of all the individual factors set at their particular levels are plotted on either side of the average line. The size of the connecting line between the two levels represents the amount that each factor contributes to the overall average when it is changed from low level to high level. The maximum attainable peel strength considering the contribution by main factors only can be calculated Eq. 1:

$$\bar{y}_{max} = \bar{y} + (\text{D contribution}) + (\text{W contribution}) + (\text{A contribution}) \quad (1)$$

4.2 Taguchi analysis

In the graphical representation of these factors, Fig. 2, the size of the lines deviating from the average indicates their contribution toward the average peel load. Therefore, from Fig. 2, the contribution of the main factors is substantial compared to the factor interaction effects. However, if the contribution of the main factors alone were considered, from Eq. 1 it yields 517N, but the average value in Table 3 when the factors D is at level 1, and W and A are at level 2 is 524N. This discrepancy in the values indicates a presence of some factor interaction.

Fig. 2 Taguchi representation of all contributing factors towards peel strength

Fig. 3 Graphical representation of interaction effects

The factor interaction effects show the influence that one factor may have on another towards the overall response. A graphical representation of the interaction effects is shown in Fig. 3, which suggests no interaction between the distance and welding time, and distance and amplitude. However, the graph in Fig. 3(c) displays a mild positive interaction between welding time and amplitude, meaning that amplitude has a positive effect at a high level of welding time. It is known that W and A determine the amount of energy produced in ultrasonic bonding [3] and in this case, the presence of mild positive factor-interaction implies that higher energy promotes effective bonding.

Therefore, a value of 90% of the total welding amplitude, a welding distance of 50% of the facing thickness and a welding time of 1s were used to ultrasonically bond the facings on to the core.

Fig. 3 Drum peel test results (a) Trial 1 (b) Trial 5

During the climbing drum peel test, it was observed that the peel strength/load in addition to the welding parameters also depended on the contact area of the facings on the core edges. As alternate rows of the cores had an additional double thickness cell wall, Fig. 3 the resistance offered toward peeling was much higher. Therefore, by increasing the cell density in the core, the peel strength can be expected to increase.

5 Flexural tests of sandwich panels

The honeycomb core shear properties were determined using ASTM C 393. Specimens of nominal length, width and height of 450mm, 80mm and 25mm respectively were prepared. A support span of 400mm and loading span of 200mm were used. A crosshead speed of 2mm/min was applied until ultimate core failure occurred and the deflection was measured with a deflectometer (Instron, model 3540).

5.1 Sandwich Panel design

When a sandwich panel is subjected to flexural loading, it typically fails in certain modes, Fig. 3. To obtain the shear strength of the cores, it is necessary that the core fails in shear, Fig. 3 (d). Therefore, the panel was designed such that it either failed by core-to-face debonding or by core shear.

The standard requires an estimation of the core shear strength and modulus to determine that the core will fail before the face sheets. A Nomex core with similar relative density was used to provide a rough approximation of the core shear strength and modulus [10], Table 4 summarises the testing requirements.

Fig. 3 Sandwich panel failure modes (a) Face sheet tensile failure (b) Face sheet wrinkling (c) Intercellular buckling (d) Core Shear

The flax/PP laminates do not satisfy three of the requirements; the longitudinal modulus of 4.80GPa and longitudinal strength of 90.5MPa were too low. Plytron™ with [0/90/0] exhibited higher longitudinal modulus of 17.5GPa and longitudinal strength of 338MPa, but fails to the flexural rigidity requirement. Therefore, additional laminates of Plytron™ with stacking sequence of [0/90/0/90/0] were used to satisfy the requirements.

It has to be noted that the fibre volume fraction in the flax/PP and glass/PP remained the same and as the bonding occurring at the interface is due to polymer melting and fusing, replacing flax/PP to glass/PP of similar fibre volume fractions will not alter the results obtained in the Taguchi analysis.

Table. 3 Summary of sandwich panel flexural test requirements

Requirements	Condi tions	Flax/PP	Plytron™	Plytron™
Stacking Sequence		[0/90/0]	[0/90/0]	[0/90/0/90/0]
Thin Face Assumption	$t_c/t_f > 10$	11	35	21
Weak Core Assumption	$E_f/E_c > 50$	14	50	50
Flexural Rigidity per Metre (Nm)	$D > 3,720$	2,600	3,470	5,500
Core Shear Strength (MPa)	$\tau_{12} \geq 2.6$	2.3	3.0	5.4
Core Compressive Strength (MPa)	$\sigma_c \leq 4.5$	1.6	2.2	4.0

Face sheet tensile failure, intercellular buckling and face sheet wrinkling failure modes were analysed (Equation 2 and 3) with failure strengths of 377MPa, 270MPa and 1.38GPa respectively, thus intercellular buckling was determined to be the predominant mode of failure which is characteristic of honeycombs with a large cell diameter [11].

$$\sigma_{cr,ib} = \frac{2E_f}{1-\nu_{12}^2} \left(\frac{t_f}{s} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{cr,fc} = 0.82E_f \left(\frac{E_c t_f}{E_f t_c} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

Where E represents the modulus, t represents thicknesses and subscript f and c represent facing and core, respectively. The parameter S in Eq.2 is diameter of the inscribed circle. The core shear and compressive strength of the core with the above values were estimated to be 4.1MPa and 3.0MPa respectively.

5.2 Results

The panels were designed such that the failure occurred due to intracellular buckling of the facings at 270MPa by assuming a perfect core-facing

interface bond. In the properties summarised in Table 4, the maximum stress experienced in the facings was ~56MPa.

Table. 4 Summary of core flexural properties

Property	Wood/PP
Cell Size, s (mm)	12.5
Core Density, ρ^* (kg/m ³)	115±7.0
Maximum Deflection, δ (mm)	1.18
Core Shear Strength, τ_{12} (MPa)	0.7±0.2
Facing Tensile Stress, σ_f (MPa)	55.85
f- facing; 1- longitudinal; 2- transverse	

Hence, the failure in sandwich panels must be either shear in the core or debonding at the core-facing interface. In Fig. 4, the failure of the core appears to have failed due to core shear but on close examination, they had failed due to debonding at the core-to-face interface. Hence, the failure in the panel was initiated due to debonding at the interface followed by core shear. The core shear strength was estimated to be 0.7 ±2.0MPa compared to that of unreinforced PP honeycombs (0.5MPa) and sisal-PP honeycombs of ~1.5MPa.

Fig. 3 Shear failure observed during flexural testing

The specific shear strengths of the wood-PP core and some standard cores are listed in Table. 5. Though the values of the wood-PP cores are similar to those of the unreinforced PP cores, it has to be understood that these values were achieved at much lower cell density and larger cell sizes. The mechanical properties of the honeycombs are proportional to the cell geometry and the cell walls dimensions, represented by either the relative density ϕ or t/l (t and l are the thickness and length of the cell wall, respectively) [12].

In this study, the t/l value of the reinforced cores was 0.07 as compared to 0.08 of the unreinforced

ones. Therefore, with the increase in the t/l value, the cell density is expected to increase, which in effect increases the double thickness cell walls, providing proportional resistance to peeling and increased core shear strength values [13].

Table.5 Specific shear strength of wood-PP cores

Material, cell size (mm)	Density (kg/m ³)	τ/ρ (Nm/kg)
Polypropylene core, ~6	49 ±12.0	8 x 10 ³
Aluminium (5056), ~10	37 ±3.0	32 x 10 ³
Nomex (Phenolic), ~10	48 ±3.0	27 x 10 ³
Sisal-PP hexagonal core, ~12	151 ±7.6	10 x 10 ³
Sisal-PP sinusoidal core, ~12	145 ±3.2	12 x 10 ³
Wood-PP hexagonal core, ~12	115±7.0	8 x 10 ³

6. Summary

Honeycomb cores from Woodfibre-PP composites were successfully manufactured using matched-die thermoforming techniques. Ultrasonic bonding methods were used effectively to reduce the hassles of conventional thermoplastic bonding methods. A full factorial DoE based on orthogonal arrays was used to examine the peel strength of the facings from the core by varying the parameters systematically at two levels. An analysis based on Taguchi method was applied to understand the synergistic effects of these parameters on the peel strength. The analysis suggested a minor interaction between the welding amplitude and welding time, indicating the increase in welding amplitude should be complimented with the welding time. However, this interaction was marginal compared to the main factor effects. All the panels at different levels failed at the core-to-face interface but the highest peel strength values were exhibited by specimens that were welded with amplitude of 22.5µm, a welding distance of 50% of the facing thickness from the welding interface and a welding time of 1s. Though the panels exhibited ~30% increase in shear strength values compared to the unreinforced cores, their specific shear strength was similar to those of the unreinforced ones (8x10³Nm/kg). However, as these were achieved at much lower cell densities or t/l values (0.07), the shear strength is expected to increase with the increase in t/l ratio and hence the core-facing interfacial bonding.

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